

genes for bacterial blight (BB), rice blast (Bl), and brown planthopper (BPH).

Two early rice varieties with medium growth duration—Xiang Zaoxian 3 and

HA793 17-4—have been selected from segregating material of IR36/ Guong jie 9. They have resistance to BB, Bl, BPH, and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH),

and high yield (see table). By 1987, they had been planted in 500,000 ha in Hubei, Jiangxi, Guongxi, and Zhejiang Provinces. □

Three rice varieties named in Ghana

R. C. Dekuku, *Crops Research Institute, P.O. Box 52, Nyankpala - Tamale, Ghana (present address: Plant Breeding Department, IIRI)*

In Ghana, rice is cultivated mostly under rainfed conditions.

C168 from the cross Intan/BPI-76-1 from the Philippines, IR1750-F5-B5 from the cross E425/IR22 from IIRI, and ToX 516-19-Sel from the cross Moroberekan/ Juma I, ToX 7-3-2-3-2, and SE3639 from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) were selected from IRTP trials early in the 1980s.

They consistently have outyielded most other varieties and local checks under rainfed lowland shallow conditions at research sites (Table 1). Even in 1983, with a Jun-Oct growing season rainfall of only 497 mm at Nyankpala and 547 mm at Manga, compared to the 30-yr average 785 mm and 794 mm, yields equaled or were higher than those of the check varieties.

On-farm test yields in 1985 and 1986 also were encouraging (Table 2), and in 1987 the Ghana Rice Varietal Release Committee accepted GR19 (C168), GR20 (IR1750-F5-B5), and GR21 (ToX 516-19-Sel) for rainfed cultivation.

GR19 (100 cm tall) matures in about 120 d; GR20 (90 cm), in 105 d; and GR21 (90 cm), in 110 d. All have acceptable cooking and eating qualities and are resistant or moderately resistant to leaf blast and brown spot. □

Table 1. Grain yield and reactions to blast and brown spot of GR19, GR20, and GR21 under rainfed conditions at research sites in Ghana, 1981-85.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)					Reaction ^a to		
	1981 (1 site)	1982 (2 sites)	1983 ^a (2 sites)	1984 (3 sites)	1985 (9 sites)	Mean ^b	Blast	Brown spot
GR19 (C168)	3.8	2.1	1.2	2.6	2.0	2.3 (46%)	2	3
GR20 (IR1750-F5-B5)	4.4	2.4	1.6	1.7	2.1	2.4 (53%)	3	2
GR21 (ToX 516-19-Sel)	4.4	2.4	1.0	2.8	2.5	2.6 (65%)	3	3
Check variety Tamale 1	2.4	1.4	1.0	1.4	1.8	1.6	7	5

^aRainfall deficit was 247-288 mm at trial sites. ^bPercentages show yield increase over check variety. ^cBy the *Standard evaluation systems for rice* scale.

Table 2. On-farm trial grain yield of GR19, GR20, and GR21 in Ghana, 1985 and 1986.

Site	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	GR19	GR21	GR20	Local check
	1985			
Nayoko	2.6	2.8	2.9	1.7
Zawse	2.2	2.8	2.8	1.6
Zabgo	0.9	1.7	2.3	2.2
Gore	0.4	0.6	1.3	0.5
Vane	3.4	4.9	2.7	2.8
Mean	1.9	2.6	2.4	1.8
	1986			
Tarkpaa 1	2.2	2.4		1.3
Tarkpaa 2	2.9	1.8		2.1
Tarkpaa 3	1.7	1.2		0.8
Cheshegu	2.4	2.2		1.4
Zuarungu	3.7	^a		2.9
Soe 1	0.9	0.8		0.7
Soe 2	5.2	5.2		5.6
Bladjei	1.5	1.6		1.1
Katiejeli	0.9	0.6		1.3
Tarkpaa 4	3.0	3.1		3.0
Kete Krachi	2.9	3.5		3.8
Kpassa/Nkwanta	^a	3.3		1.4
Central Volta	2.6	2.9		1.0
Gbefi	3.3	3.9		1.2
Vane	^a	2.3		2.0
Mean	2.6	2.5		2.0

^aNot included.

Red Triveni, a promising short-duration variety for India

K. Karunakaran, K. I. James, C. A. Rosamma, P. Chandrika, and N. R. Nair, *Regional Agricultural Research Station, Pattambi 679306, India*

Of three short-duration, semidwarf, high-yielding rice varieties released in Kerala, Triveni is the most popular among Kerala farmers. Farmers who have a strong preference for red grain have been asking for a red-grained version, adaptable to all growing seasons.

About 5 yr after Triveni's release, a few isolated red-grained plants were found. Red-grained plants reoccurred, despite strict roguing.

White-grained PTB15, one of the parents in the evolution of Triveni, has purple tipping. Possibly, segregation for

an inhibitory factor caused the red-grained plants.

Single plant selection and progeny testing were carried out systematically and the nonsegregating red lines bulked and multiplied. The new line was designated Red Triveni and tested in replicated yield trials during the three main rice seasons 1985-86.

The new culture with red grain uniformly performed well during the three seasons (see table). In adaptive trials in farmers' fields in three districts

Performance of Red Triveni in wet, dry, and summer seasons. Pattambi, Kerala, India, 1985-86.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering			Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Summer	Kharif	Rabi	Summer 1985-86	Kharif 1986	Rabi 1986
Red Triveni	78	94	74	4.8	4.1	3.3
Triveni	78	94	78	4.4	3.8	2.7
Annapoorna	77	89	67	4.3	3.7	2.6
Rohini	76	99	65	4.3	3.8	2.4
LSD (P = 0.05)				ns	ns	0.2

in summer season 1987, Red Triveni yields averaged 6 t/ha (yields of the

original white-grained Triveni averaged 5.2 t/ha). □

A blast (Bl)-resistant and high-yielding early indica variety

Xiong Zhenmin and Wang Guoliang, China
National Rice Research Institute, Hangzhou, China

Fu 8-1 is a newly released semidwarf indica variety induced from variety 8004 with Co⁶⁰ r-ray (3.5 krad). It has 115-120 d duration, 1-2 d earlier than popular local variety Guang-Lu-Ai 4, with wide adaptability in Zhejiang,

Jiangxi, Hunan, and Hubei Provinces (26.0-31.0°N, 114-120°E).

The new variety performed well in the regional trials of Zhejiang Province in 1986 and 1987—average yields 7.5 t/ha, nearly 9% higher than Guang-Lu-Ai 4 (Table 1). Grain quality is also better.

An outstanding characteristic of Fu 8-1 is its widespectrum resistance to rice Bl caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*. In 1986 artificial inoculation tests, it was resistant to 26 and moderately resistant to 1 of 29 local isolates (Table 2). It also has good field resistance. □

Table 1. Some agronomic characteristics^a of Fu 8-1. Hangzhou, China, 1986-87.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Seed set (%)	Yield ^a (t/ha)
Fu 8-1	114	75.8	472.26	69.7	32.2	76.6	7.5
Guang-Lu-Ai 4	114	67.4	533.73	66.7	25.2	78.1	6.9

^aMean of 7 sites.

Table 2. Reaction of Fu 8-1 to 29 *P. oryzae* isolates belonging to groups A to G.^a Hangzhou, China, 1986-87.

Variety	Reaction ^b																												
	A7		B11				B15				B3			B19		C15		D3			D7		E1		E3		G1		
	15-1	14-2	18-9	31-2	34-2	52-3	15-4	15-1	20-2	51-4	51-4	64-4	18-5	43-1	83-4	14-1	90-1	71-1	82-1	85-4	49-4	36-3	49-4	46-2	16-1	6-3	7-2	21-2	9-3
Fu 8-1	M	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Guang-Lu-Ai4	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	S	S	M	R	S	S	S	S	S

^aGrouping based on Chinese differentials. Each letter is followed by the race number in that group. ^bR = resistant, M = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

OM91: an improved rice variety for high-production irrigated areas

Nguyen van Luat, Pham cong Voc, and Nguyen van Loan, Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Institute (CLRRI), Omon, Haugiang, Vietnam

OM91 was found to be widely adapted in several provincial trials. It has higher

Table 1. Yield of OM91 at CLRRI, Omon Haugiang, Vietnam, 1984-86.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)					Average
	Dry season			Wet season		
	1983	1984	1985	1984	1985	
OM91	4.6	4.4	5.8	6.8	4.5	5.8
NN7A	4.8	3.9	5.7	6.3	4.5	5.0
LSD %	0.7	0.6	0.7	0.6	0.4	—
CV (%)	7.3	13.7	14.6	13.7	14.6	—